

ICCM22

MELBOURNE AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Nonlinear low-velocity impact response of sandwich beams with functionally graded negative Poisson's ratio honeycomb core

Presenter: Chong LI

Supervisor: Prof. Hai WANG
Prof. H-S SHEN*

Major: Solid Mechanics

Date: Tuesday, 13 Aug

上海交通大学

SHANGHAI JIAO TONG UNIVERSITY

- 1 Introduction
- 2 Novelty
- 3 Methods
- 4 Results and Discussion
- 5 Concluding Remarks

- Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)

- The term 'auxetic' was introduced by Evans[1].
- Comparison of Non-auxetic and auxetic materials[2]:

[1] Evans K E, Nkansah M A, Hutchinson I J, et al. Molecular network design. *Nature*, 1991, 353: 124.

[2] Alderson A. A triumph of lateral thought. *Chemistry & Industry*, 1999, 17: 384.

- Mechanical properties of NPR
- Indentation Resistance

- Deformational Behavior

Non-auxetic:
anticlastic curvature
(ASTM D6790M-16)

- The applications of NPR
- Aerospace: vanes for aircraft gas-turbine engines [3]
- Biomedicine [4]
- Defense [2]:

[3] C. Lira, F. Scarpa, R. Rajasekaran. A Gradient Cellular Core for Aeroengine Fan Blades Based on Auxetic Configurations. *J. Intelligent Mat. Systems Struct.*, 2011, 22: 907.

[4] Evans K E, Alderson A. Auxetic materials: functional materials and structures from lateral thinking. *Adv. Mat.*, 2000, 12: 617.

- Functionally graded (FG)
- This concept begins from the research to Metal-Ceramic composites by Japanese researchers [5], and then been introduced to fiber-reinforced composites and CNTRC [6].

Function/ Property	① Mechanical Strength ② Thermal Conductivity		
Structure/ Texture	Constituent Elements: Ceramics (○) Metal (●) Fiber (◇+) Micropore (○)		
Materials	Example	FGM	non-FGM

[5] 新野正之, 平井敏雄, 渡辺龙三. 日本复合材料学会志. 1987,10:1-8.

[6] Shen H-S. *Composite Structures*, 2009, 91: 9-19.

- Functionally graded (FG)
- The FG cellular solid materials:
 - Better designability
 - Continuous distribution of properties, e.g. stiffness [7]
- The FG-NPR cellular solid materials in the existing literatures, are honeycomb materials with its cell wall angles or cell thickness graded in one of its **in-plane** directions.
- We introduce this concept to the **thickness direction** of sandwich beams, and propose three types of FG configurations, which are then compared with the Uniform Distribution (i.e. UD) configuration.

**FG-X
Honeycomb**

[7] Hou Y, Tai YH, Lira C, et al. The bending and failure of sandwich structures with auxetic gradient cellular cores. *Compos Part A* 2013; 49:119-31.

- Research initiation
- In 1987, open cell foams with negative Poisson's ratio (NPR) were manufactured by Lakes[8], who then gave an idealized reentrant unit cell:

- Following this, many different **micro-structures** have been came up with:

[8] Lakes R S. Foam structures with a negative Poisson's ratio. *Science*, 1987, 235: 1038-1040.

- Research limitations
 - Structural Configuration
- Existing research. Many papers are presented, but most of them are using honeycombs, which have the same out-of-plane directions with the sandwich structures.
- However, when the sandwich structures are subjected to out-of-plane blast or impact loads, they can't response in a negative Poisson's ratio way.

- Present models. The core is arranged to have an out-of-plane direction as Y-direction, which is different from that of the sandwich beam (Z-direction), as shown below.

- Research limitations
 - Ways to handle cores
- Existing research. Most of them use effective properties of the core to represent them.
- However,
 - ☹ some parameters do not have accurate solution, e.g. G_{23} for honeycomb [9],
 - ☹ the effective parameters are the function of deformation, and existing solutions are for linear stage.

- Present models. For nonlinear problems, it is necessary to use 3D FEM to investigate the response more properly.

[9] Gibson LJ, Ashby MF. Cellular solids: structure and properties. second ed. Cambridge: **Cambridge University Press**; 1997.

[10] Hui Wan et al. A study of negative Poisson's ratios in auxetic honeycombs based on a large deflection model. *European Journal of Mechanics A/Solids*, 2004, 23: 95-106.

- Based on the discussion to existing research limitations, we then sum up the novelty of present research:
 - ✓ Both the **NPR core** and **functionally graded pattern** are taken into account.
 - ✓ The core is arranged to have an **out-of-plane direction** as Y-direction, which is different from that of the sandwich beam.

• 3D FEM:

- Modeling all the details, not to use the equivalent layers.

• Effects of NPR configurations

- As illustrated in Fig.1, when the sandwich beam is subjected to an out-of-plane impact, the core materials in the region close to the impact area will “**flow**” towards mid-span cross section, which indicate that in this volume the strain along the X-direction $\varepsilon_1 < 0$.
- Meanwhile, the strain along thickness direction (Z-direction) $\varepsilon_3 < 0$, the effective Poisson’s ratio is therefore $\nu_{31} = -\varepsilon_1 / \varepsilon_3 < 0$.

Fig. 1

- Indentation of sandwich beams with different honeycomb core
- The thickness decrease of the sandwich beams with UD (-20) honeycomb core is distinctly smaller than that of UD (+20) beam.
- The difference between different configurations with NPR is evidently
- Moreover, the FG-V beam has the lowest curve, meaning a highest impact resistance.

Fig. 2

- ✓ In the present work*, we focus our attention on the nonlinear low-velocity impact response of sandwich beams with FG-NPR honeycomb core. The novelty of this study is that the NPR core and functionally graded pattern are both taken into account. 3D full scale finite element simulations are conducted.
- ✓ The core is arranged to have an out-of-plane direction as Y -direction, which is different from that of the sandwich beam (Z -direction), as shown in **Fig. 1**. In such a layout, when the sandwich beam is subjected to an out-of-plane impact, the auxetic core will response in an in-plane NPR behavior.
- ✓ In conclusion, the NPR characteristic of core can remarkably reduce the thickness decrease of sandwich beams when subjected to an out-of-plane impact, and the FG configurations will distinctly influence the impact response.

* **Acknowledge:** The support for this work, provided by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under Grant 51779138 is gratefully acknowledged.

Thank you !

&

Welcome to SJTU

Chong LI, H-S SHEN, Hai WANG

lichong@sjtu.edu.cn